

Recommendations for Developing a Metadata Profile for Earth System Science Data

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Publication date: June, 2022

Executive Summary

Most Earth System Science (ESS) research projects are data driven and/or produce data sets as main results. Metadata management is core to support discovery and reuse of such results, and ultimately to allow for reproducibility of the research findings. Thus, ensuring acquisition and provision of meaningful and quality assured metadata should become an integral part of such projects. Here, choosing a suitable metadata schema and/or developing a proper metadata profile is a relevant task at the beginning of each project. Building on available, well-known and well-used, often standardized formats and schemas is strongly recommended.

This document serves as guideline for researchers, who need to manage metadata with certain project-specific requirements. It guides metadata managers to create a suitable metadata schema, which meets the project-specific requirements. Metadata consumers will get an overview about relevant aspects, basic principles and standards to understand available metadata and to aggregate or summarize metadata for their purposes.

This guide starts with a short introduction, followed by an overview about the stepwise development of a metadata schema or profile. All necessary steps will be explained and underpinned with links for further readings to keep this document short. The metadata schema developed in the GeoKur research project (<https://geokur.geo.tu-dresden.de/>) serves as the blueprint for this guide.

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Introduction

To enable an efficient research data management (RDM) including data publication, structured metadata need to be acquired and provided. Metadata play a major role in each of the phases of the research data lifecycle. From a user's point of view, metadata supports finding, comparison and evaluation of available data during discovery. In the creation and processing phases, metadata describe processes and interim results, in particular to support an efficient collaborative work. Finally, metadata enable discovery and evaluation of fitness for use as well as getting access and usage information when the scientific results are published.

Figure1: Research Data Lifecycle (<https://www.gfbio.org/training/materials/data-lifecycle/plan>)

The process to develop a project-specific metadata schema should be performed at the beginning of the project to support the efficient usage of RDM software. The developed metadata schema serves as basis for (project intern) research data management and for metadata generation processes. In the RDM platform, the schema enables the structured storage, linking and discovery of available data. During data creation and processing, the metadata schema is relevant for automated metadata generation, e.g. by script annotations.

In ESS, data are often created and used in heterogeneous and interdisciplinary research projects. Therefore, the requirements for a suitable metadata schema differ and available metadata schemas often do not fully meet these requirements. Here, we describe the process to develop a project-specific schema.

Process to develop project-specific metadata schema for ESS or related cross-domain data

Developing a project-specific metadata schema or profile is a complex process considering common (research) principles, user requirements and software settings. The process includes a sequence of decision points considering the general and common aspects first and afterwards formal and more detailed aspects. The first steps include the review and choice of relevant available principles and standards. Project-specific requirements, which are not met by available standards should then be modelled as extension points.

The process to develop project-specific metadata schema includes the following steps:

S1: Common principles

Select or define common principles, which are relevant for an integrated management of metadata and data publications. This includes decisions about role and right managements.

S2: General recommendations

Consider a set of general metadata-related recommendations prior to developing a specific metadata profile and management regime.

S3: Project- and domain-specific requirements for the metadata profile

Identify relevant project-specific requirements for the metadata profile, as a basis for the latter selection and extension of existing metadata standards.

S4: Review existing metadata standards

Review existing metadata standards and choose a standard based on your requirements.

S5: Mark and integrate extension points

Prepare a synopsis of missing and unnecessary elements in the chosen schema. If required add new elements, remove the obligations for less important elements or add obligations for important elements.

These five steps will be outlined in the following sections.

S1. Select relevant core principles

Several communities currently discuss aspects and methods of RDM and the vision of openness, reuse and reproducibility, in general or for certain research domains on several levels of details, e.g. regarding roles, metadata and data.

The following list provides an overview of prominent principles and concepts in RDM and their relevance for metadata and provides links to further information and related tools.

Open Science, Open Data and Reproducible Science

The Open Science movement aims to make scientific research and its results openly accessible. Open Science summarizes the principles open methodology, open source, open data, open access, open peer review and open educational resources. Open Data aims on providing data that can be (re-)used freely and redistributed. Reproducible Science complements Open Data aspects to make all data processing steps of scientific results transparent, thus to allow for reproducing these steps and the processing results.

Relevance for developing a metadata schema:

To make data open¹, an open license should be applied, the data should be made available (in a machine-readable format), e.g. via download or an API, in an open format and the data should be discoverable. Information about the chosen license, usage options such as available data format(s), as well as common descriptions to discover the data should be included in the metadata schema. Additional information about the dataset's provenance, e.g. tools and scripts applied for data processing, and about the quality of the data further enhances transparency and reproducibility.

Further readings:

Open Data

- The Open Knowledge Foundation: <https://okfn.org/opendata/how-to-open-data/>
- The Open Data Handbook <http://opendatahandbook.org/guide/en/>
- Open Definition: <https://opendefinition.org/>
- GEOLabel: <https://www.geolabel.info/>
- Open Data Label: <https://www.opendatainside.com/de/>

Common and Earth System Science Communities

- German Reproducibility Network: <https://reproducibilitynetwork.de/>
- NFDI4Earth Research Software and Reproducibility Interest Group: <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/participate/get-involved-by-interest-groups/ig-geo-researchsoftware-reproducibility>
- OSGEO and Open Geoscience: <https://www.osgeo.org/initiatives/open-geoscience/>
- Free and Open Source Software For Geospatial : <https://www.osgeo.org/initiatives/foss4g/>

Projects

- Opening Reproducible Research project: <https://o2r.info/>
- Open AIRE: <https://www.openaire.eu/>
- European Open Science Cloud: Strategy https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/open_consultation_booklet_sria-eosc_20-july-2020.pdf
- Open Science Community Starter Kit: <https://inosc-starter-kit.netlify.app/>

¹ <http://opendatahandbook.org/guide/en/how-to-open-up-data/>

FAIR

The FAIR principles serve as common concept in (research) data management and provide guidelines to improve the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reuse of digital objects (see links below for detailed descriptions of the principles).

Several communities and projects started to develop practical implementations related to the FAIR principles, metrics to measure the level of FAIRness of offered data sets have been developed. The suggested solutions are either generic or domain-specific.

Relevance for developing a metadata schema:

The metadata schema should enable users to find and access suitable data for their use cases. Therefore, in a simplified view, the schema should include (structured) fields for spatial, thematic and temporal information of the data as well as information on how to access the data, e.g. download links or links to related APIs or (standard-based) services.

When developing an ESS-specific schema for research data, several principles are of particular interest, for instance to provide metadata fields/attributes for

- linking to descriptions of the measurement device or to the platform for measurement data
- additional information on the methodology used to generate the data sets, e.g. by linking to related publications or processing scripts
- providing descriptions processing steps as basis for data provenance information
- enabling interdisciplinary data usage, e.g. by linking to controlled vocabularies², registries and ontologies
- providing descriptive information about quality, e.g. by controlled vocabularies for metrics descriptions, including information sources, and linking ground truth data sets.

Further readings:

Literature

- Wilkinson et al. (2016), The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship, Scientific Data 3, DOI: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18

Common Research and Earth System Science Communities

- FAIR DO Forum: <https://fairdo.org/>
- ENVRI³ FAIR community: <https://envri.eu/home-envri-fair/>
- NFDI4Earth⁴ FAIR Data Interest Group: <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/participate/get-involved-by-interest-groups/ig-fair-data-interoperability>
- OGC⁵: <https://www.ogc.org/standards>
- RDA⁶ Working Groups: FAIRsharing Registry⁷, CURE-FAIR⁸, FAIR Data Maturity Model⁹, FAIR4RS¹⁰:

Projects

- GO FAIR project: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

² A controlled vocabulary is an organised arrangement of words and phrases used to index content and/or to retrieve content through browsing or searching. It typically includes preferred and variant terms and has a defined scope or describes a specific domain, cited from: <https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/drafts/latest/#scope-of-the-revision>

³ Environmental Research Infrastructures: <https://envri.eu/>

⁴ NFDI for Earth System Sciences: <https://www.nfdi4earth.de>

⁵ Open Geospatial Consortium: <https://www.ogc.org/>

⁶ Research Data Alliance: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/fairsharing-registry-connecting-data-policies-standards-databases.html>

⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/cure-fair-wg>

⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-data-maturity-model-wg>

¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-research-software-fair4rs-wg>

- FAIRsFAIR project: <https://www.fairsfair.eu/>
- OpenAIRE project: <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-make-your-data-fair>

HORIZON2020 Programme: Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf Guidelines and Metrics

- EOSC FAIR Metrics¹¹
- 6 Recommendations for Implementation of FAIR Practice¹²

Selected Tools

- FAIR Data tools: <https://www.dtls.nl/fair-data/find-fair-data-tools/#seventh>
- FAIR-AWARE <https://www.fairsfair.eu/fair-aware>
- F-UJI <https://www.fairsfair.eu/f-ujl-automated-fair-data-assessment-tool>

S2. Consider a set of general metadata-related recommendations

When developing or extending a metadata schema, several recommendations should be considered regardless of the scientific domain. The following list summarizes these recommendations:

R1: Reduction of efforts to create metadata

Support the users to create metadata easily and with a minimal manual effort. This includes using proper tools to support the creation process and establishing a compact metadata schema, which only covers useful and used information.

- Focus on a limited number of metadata elements
 - Reduce the number of metadata elements by selecting meaningful metadata elements for the schema or at least by setting proper obligations, by avoiding duplicated information storage and by linking to available information resources (see R3, R4).
- Provide several options to publish metadata, such as
 - Online catalogue forms with pre-filled templates, e.g. <https://docs.ckan.org/en/2.9/theming/templates.html>
 - Excel sheets with wrapper tools¹³ to generate XML that can be published via APIs,
 - Annotation schemas that enable generating metadata based on annotated scripts
 - Serialization scripts, e.g. for generating provenance information¹⁴
- Provide short and comprehensive guidance on how to fill metadata elements correctly
 - Provide fact sheets or FAQ for tools and metadata elements
 - Explain terms with help texts in user interfaces

R2: Linkages to available metadata

Define metadata elements with options to provide information as a reference or link to attributes of other already published metadata (sets), available via catalogues or

¹¹ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1jcfA2eF-UL0nxTcQyNbMyJAbZCOqh9WvPy7RRtsTKk/edit>

¹² <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/4630fa57-1348-11eb-9a54-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

¹³ https://github.com/GeoinformationSystems/CSV2ISO_XML

¹⁴ <https://github.com/GeoinformationSystems/ProvlT>

repositories. This should include linking to metadata in other formats/schemata than the provided schema.

- Link to available structured metadata instead of including elements (and sub-elements) in the schema.
- Figure 2 gives an overview of frequently available information in metadata, which should be linked, e.g. linking to publisher information via orcid or link from XML metadata to detailed provenance information stored in PROV-O/RDF

Figure 2: Linkable information in metadata (own illustration)

- Persistent identifiers play a major role in citing available information. A persistent identifier (PID) is a long-lasting reference to a description, e.g. mostly distinguished in those for objects, such as for publications, datasets or software, and those for persons. The guidance document¹⁵ to choose a PID contains a summary of available PIDs and related registers.

R3: Linkages to external vocabularies, registries and ontologies

Support users in linking to existing vocabularies, registries and ontologies and even specify mandatory reference linkages for some metadata elements. This supports comparisons of different metadata sets, reduce individual stored descriptions, and allows an efficient update of definitions and descriptions in the registries or ontologies instead of updating several metadata. Common external vocabularies also support the automatic translation of terms. It also supports automatic reasoning: Data portals use vocabularies to widen search queries by linking to related terms in the vocabularies (e.g. synonyms, wider or narrower terms in the hierarchy).

¹⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/4192174#.YFMSbj1KjZ8>

Table 1: Selected external controlled vocabularies and registries

Name	Short description and links
European Petroleum Survey Group Geodesy (EPSG)	<p>The EPSG code references and uniquely identifies the used coordinate reference system. Several registries do exist:</p> <p>http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/ https://epsg.org/</p>
Domain specific vocabularies and ontologies	<p>Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Contains several ESS related elements, not only focussing on topics, but also including acronyms, instrument and sensor descriptions, or other ESS related terms. https://vocabs.ardc.edu.au/search/#!/?activeTab=vocabularies&pp=15&q=&v_p=1&r_p=1&r_collapse_expand=vocabularyIdIri&v_publisher=National%20Aeronautics%20and%20Space%20Administration</p> <p>AgroVoc Describes agricultural concepts, terms, definitions and relationships for cross-domain usage. http://www.fao.org/agrovoc/search</p> <p>General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus (GEMET) Describes environmental themes including INSPIRE Spatial Data Themes. https://www.eionet.europa.eu/gemet/en/themes/</p> <p>An overview of available ESS vocabularies and ontologies is provided by the Research Data Alliance https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Ij3nXherJWW5wmpyHYkxQUHJJaSeney1fGHT0SasM0/edit#gid=1725001098</p> <p>Furthermore, the ontology search provides a list of available ontologies: https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/index</p>
License and access information	<p>Creative Commons Licenses https://creativecommons.org/licenses/</p> <p>INSPIRE Limitations on Public Access Code list https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/metadata-codelist/LimitationsOnPublicAccess</p> <p>INSPIRE Conditions Applying to Access Code list https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/metadata-codelist/ConditionsApplyingToAccessAndUse</p> <p>CrossRef https://www.crossref.org/education/content-registration/administrative-metadata/license-information/</p>
Registries for people and organizations	<p>orcid researcher register https://orcid.org/</p> <p>Research Organization Registry https://ror.org/about/</p>

A list of automatically discovered ontologies is available on the DBPedia Archivio website¹⁶.

¹⁶ <https://archivo.dbpedia.org/list>

R4: Enable automation

Relevant metadata processes should be automated. This includes Integrating metadata creation in the data production processes and using automatically extracted metadata to avoid information loss and to reduce the manual efforts for creating and updating metadata (R1). Use available metadata creation tools, scripts or annotation concepts.

- Provide tools for the extraction of metadata, e.g. extract specific quality information from geodata¹⁷, to facilitate adding new or checking existing metadata for workflow inputs or to support quality assurance for analysis results.
- Enable schema mapping tools to generate standardized metadata from domain-specific (modelling) metadata, like ArcGIS model builder workflow descriptions to PROV-O¹⁸.
- Enable usage of metadata in software (machine-readable) and by the researchers (human-readable). Consider unique identifiers as an example (for machine-readable), which are formatted using human-readable texts (e.g. include structure of datasets in the identifier `id=landuse_series:crops:wheat` instead of `id=12`).

R5: Provide review and update mechanism for metadata

During the project, certain metadata might change over time or need to be complemented. These changes address locally stored metadata, e.g. new publications are available and need to be referenced, affiliations of data producers has changed, or project websites will not be available after the funding period ends – or linked information, e.g. links to external information or content have been changed, e.g. caused by restructuring/updating registries/vocabularies. Therefore, an update concept should be provided, including

- Regular reviews
- With a differentiated update strategy for input datasets, interim results, and data sets as main results of analysis
- Supported by proper tools

S3. Identify project- and domain-specific requirements for the metadata schema

Identifying project- and domain-specific requirements for the metadata schema is a complex process, which can be organized along several perspectives – e.g. collecting information needs within the project and structuring the collection regarding metadata scope / elements of metadata standards. The following checklist is intended to facilitate information gathering:

Checklist for available information structured as metadata scopes

Do you need to provide and link the following information?

C1: Structuring of data

Datasets in the project might be structured in hierarchies or data series / subsets, according dataset's versions or linked to other via qualified relations, e.g. indicating similar contents.

Datasets are often related to other datasets, e.g. to previous versions or inputs. Typically, persistent identifiers, such as DOI¹⁹ or catalogue URL/URNs, are used.

¹⁷ <https://github.com/GeoinformationSystems/MetadataFromGeodata>

¹⁸ <https://github.com/GeoinformationSystems/ArcGIS2ProvO>

¹⁹ Persistent identifier for physical, digital and abstract objects. Researchers use DOI to register scientific articles or related samples. Further information is available here: <https://www.doi.org/>

C2: Data formats and services

Datasets are stored in community-specific and standardized data formats, which can be referenced, e.g. geodata are available via OGC²⁰ Web services.

C3: Scientific results and publications

The project provides scientific results as datasets with related publications. Frequently used persistent identifiers to describe scientific results and researchers, e.g. orcid and DOI, are used.

Decide whether long-term storage and related persistent identifiers play a role in the project.

Check for available DOI or accessible websites with details about the related publications.

C4: Open data and licensing

Provided data is licensed as open data or under licenses, which can be cited.

Even if you are going to provide all data as open data without any usage restrictions, you need to link a proper license.

C5: Quality information

Quality information plays an essential role. To facilitate the evaluation of fitness for use, detailed quality information for relevant datasets should be provided..

Data generated and provided in research projects fulfil high quality standards. Providing detailed quality information, facilitates researchers in comparing and evaluating the fitness for use of provided datasets.

C6: Provenance information

The provenance of the datasets plays an essential role in the project. The provided datasets should be described with detailed provenance information to facilitate the evaluation of fitness for use.

Provenance information, describing the workflow to generate data, is strongly linked to quality information, describing characteristics of the data that result from certain workflow steps.

C7: Thematic linking and vocabularies

In the project, a certain set of vocabularies/registries/ontologies is used to describe the provided datasets. They can be cited and linked.

This includes domain-specific vocabularies for i.e. thematic descriptions or spatial reference systems as well as registries for data formats or license information.

C8: Metadata standards and standard interface

Datasets or metadata in the project need to be compliant to a certain standard or usable via a certain interface

To show how to summarize project-specific aspects, we provide our GeoKur project as an example: The GeoKur²¹ research project aims to support the curation and quality assurance of environmental research data for the use case of global land use data. The developments include approaches to support Research Data Management for the discovery, reuse, and collaboration across disciplines and including heterogeneous data sources. Within the project, data producers, data consumers, and software engineers collaborate to develop a common understanding of data quality to foster transparency and reuse of created data.

²⁰ Open Geospatial Consortium provides standards to publish and share geodata. Further information is available here: <https://www.ogc.org/>

²¹ <https://geokur.geo.tu-dresden.de/>

The following aspects are relevant for developing a proper metadata schema for GeoKur:

- **Heterogeneous inputs:** In research on global land-use dynamics, a long-standing gap in global change and sustainability-related sciences can be addressed by developing consistent data products on the recent global dynamics in multiple land-use variables. Within the project, several datasets from different sources are used as inputs for statistical models, being described in heterogeneous information sources with different levels of granularity, vocabularies/ontologies, quality measures and metrics
- **Quality:** When integrating and harmonizing heterogeneous data sources through advanced statistical modelling techniques, several quality aspects, such as uncertainties in the datasets, play a major role. Quality information is required to evaluate input data sets as well as to curate and assure created products. In the project, the validation and continuous quality improvement of global land-use data by detecting, quantifying and ultimately reducing uncertainties in various sources of primary data inputs into land-use models is supported. Challenges include, amongst others, concepts for linking and comparing quality measures, e.g. in a quality ontology/register, or adding and referencing additional information, like training data or information sources.
- **Provenance:** To evaluate the fitness for use of a dataset, the provenance information is crucial. However, provenance information is often provided as unstructured text in scientific publications and does not meet the researcher's requirements on detailed and structured information that can be used in discovery or analysis tools. In our project, researchers need geo-dashboards providing linked views on provenance and quality information to identify the impact of quality parameters for certain datasets btw. for certain regions, time periods and themes, in the provenance graph.
- **Ontologies:** Spatial, temporal and thematic resolution of land-use change data as used in the project have increased, and so has the diversity of requirements of such data from different disciplines, sectors, and application domains. Ontologies and related tools support comprehensive and consistent work with heterogeneous land-use change data. In the GeoKur project, we use ontologies to model land use themes, quality measures, provenance information and geospatial workflow semantics.
- Furthermore, we implement common principles, such as FAIR concepts, and set up a research data management infrastructure with several implemented prototypes as proof-of-concept.

After identifying relevant aspects or requirements, defining common project-specific conventions for descriptions becomes a relevant task. As the conventions should be applied to describe all data sets, including inputs and data products, they should be defined and applied from the project's beginning on. The following list provides examples for such conventions:

- **Dataset's names:** Names of datasets are of particular interest, because they are displayed prominently in repositories / catalogues and are often prioritized for discovery. Names could include
 - o Scientific model name, scenarios, storylines, when used to describe model output – the same combination could then be used to generate a human- and machine-readable ID / URN, e.g. <modelname>:<scenarioname>:<topic>
 - o Spatial extent, such as the name of the region of the dataset
 - o Topic by using a term of a vocabulary, which is used in the project, although be partly redundant to keywords / topic descriptions
 - o Acronym of the providing organization, if helpful for discovery
 - o Project name, if target repository will include several projects results or internally useful to distinguish inputs (without project name) and outputs of the project (project name should be included)

- **Research organizations:** Provide a common method to structure organization name, e.g. as full name, as acronym or as a combination and decide whether sub groups need to be distinguished
 - o Geoinformatics, Technische Universität Dresden (recommended)
 - o Technische Universität
 - o TU Dresden
 - o TUD
- **Reference system:** When data needs to be integrated, it might be useful to choose a common reference system, e.g.
 - o EPSG:4326: WGS 84: <http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/OGC/1.3/CRS84>
- **Data formats:** Some domain-specific data or tools require domain-specific formats, which should follow standards²² or at least domain-specific quasi-standards, e.g.
 - o GeoPackage
 - o GeoTIFF
 - o NetCDF
 - o ESRI ArcGIS

S4: Review available metadata standards

Nowadays, lots of metadata standards, quasi standards and guidelines exists. The metadata scope and the following criteria facilitate choosing a suitable existing metadata schema: the acceptance and usage in the related community, requirements of the data publication platform / archive, supported formats and tools, and available extension points and mappings to other schemas. The following table provides a selected list of frequently used metadata standards in Geosciences.

Table 2: Selected metadata schemas for ESS, cross-domain or related domains; sorted alphabetically

Name	Short description and links	Domain
Access to Biological Collection Data (ABCD)	ABCD describes data about specimens and observations. Used in several portals, such as gfbio ²³ . https://abcd.tdwg.org	Biology, Biodiversity
Darwin Core	Darwin Core describes and structures information about biological diversity as observations, specimens, samples and related information. Used in long-term storage repositories, such as PANGAEA ²⁴ . https://dwc.tdwg.org/	Biology, Biodiversity
DataCite	DataCite provides a schema to describe and document research data. It focuses on accurate and consistent identification for citation and retrieval.	Not specific

²² A selected list of available format for Earth Sciences is available here: <https://earthdata.nasa.gov/esdis/eso/standards-and-references>

²³ <https://www.gfbio.org/de/materials>

²⁴ <https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Metadata>

Name	Short description and links	Domain
	Used in the DataCite portal ²⁵ and several other portals or repositories ²⁶ . https://schema.datacite.org	
Data Documentat ion Initiative (DDI)	DDI describes data produced by surveys and other observational methods in the social, behavioral, economic, and health sciences. Used in several portals and repository ²⁷ , e.g. SAO/NASA Astrophysics Data System Dataverse ²⁸ . https://ddialliance.org	Cross-domain
Dublin Core; ISO 15836- 1:2017	Dublin core provides a vocabulary for cross-domain resource description. ISO 15836-1:2017 summarizes core metadata elements of Dublin Core. Used in several portals ²⁹ , such as e.g. EDI Data Portal ³⁰ formerly LTER Repository, and in further research portals, because it is shipped as one the default metadata profiles in the Geonetwork ³¹ open source metadata catalogue. https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/ https://www.iso.org/standard/71339.html	Cross-domain
Ecological Metadata Language (EML)	EML describes research data in earth and environmental sciences. Used in several portals ³² , e.g. WDC portals, LTER portal. https://eml.ecoinformatics.org	Ecology
EOSC-EDMI	EOSC-EDMI provides a minimum set of metadata to find and access datasets. Provided by the European Open Science Cloud and mapped to several schemas, e.g. to DataCite and to schema.org ³³ https://eosc-edmi.github.io/	Not specific

²⁵ <https://datacite.org>

²⁶ <https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&metadataStandards%5B%5D=DataCite%20Metadata%20Schema&sort=name>

²⁷ <https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&metadataStandards%5B%5D=DDI%20-%20Data%20Documentation%20Initiative>

²⁸ <https://dataverse.harvard.edu/dataverse/ADS>

²⁹

<https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&subjects%5B%5D=34%20Geosciences%20%28including%20Geography%29&metadataStandards%5B%5D=Dublin%20Core>

³⁰ <https://portal.edirepository.org/nis/home.jsp>

³¹ <https://geonetwork-opensource.org>

³²

<https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&subjects%5B%5D=34%20Geosciences%20%28including%20Geography%29&metadataStandards%5B%5D=EML%20-%20Ecological%20Metadata%20Language>

³³ <https://eosc-edmi.github.io/crosswalk>

Name	Short description and links	Domain
GeoDCAT, DCAT	<p>GeoDCAT-AP is an extension to the “DCAT application profile for European data portals” (DCAT-AP) for the representation of geographic metadata. It enables the description of INSPIRE / ISO 19139 metadata in a format compliant with the DCAT-AP specification.</p> <p>Supported by the European Union³⁴ to implement INSPIRE and used in several European public authority portals. DCAT is frequently used in Open Data Portals, as it is one of the shipped standards of the CKAN³⁵ open source tool to implement open data websites.</p> <p>https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/good-practice/geodcat-ap, https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/</p>	Geosciences
<p>ISO 19115-1:2014 Geographic information - Metadata, ISO 19119:2016 Geographic information - Services, ISO/TS 19139:2007 Geographic information - Metadata - XML schema implementation</p>	<p>The ISO standards are used to describe geographic information and services as structured XML document.</p> <p>Recommended by NASA³⁶ and frequently used in public authority geoportals, such as Geoportal.de³⁷ or scientific geodata infrastructures, because it is shipped as one the default metadata profiles in the Geonetwork³⁸ open source metadata catalogue.</p> <p>https://www.iso.org/standard/53798.html https://www.iso.org/standard/59221.html https://www.iso.org/standard/32557.html</p>	Geosciences
OpenAIRE Guidelines für Data Archives	<p>OpenAIRE³⁹ Guidelines für Data Archives aims to structure information about publications and related datasets, supplementary material and project descriptions.</p> <p>https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/data/introduction.html</p>	Not specific
Open Archives Initiative Object Reuse and Exchange (OAI-ORE)	<p>OAI-ORE defines standards for the description and exchange of aggregations of Web resources.</p> <p>Used in several portals, e.g. EDI Data Portal⁴⁰ formerly LTER repository Repository.</p> <p>https://www.openarchives.org/ore/</p>	Not specific

³⁴ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/semantic-interoperability-community-semic/solution/geodcat-application-profile-data-portals-europe>

³⁵ <https://ckan.org/>

³⁶ <https://earthdata.nasa.gov/esdis/eso/standards-and-references#metadata>

³⁷ www.geoportal.de

³⁸ <https://geonetwork-opensource.org>

³⁹ <https://www.openaire.eu>

⁴⁰ <https://portal.edirepository.org/nis/home.jsp>

Name	Short description and links	Domain
Schema.org	Schema.org provides a vocabulary to describe data, such as datasets or articles. It was originally based on DCAT, which in turn used Dublin Core and FOAF terms. Several community extensions are hosted to address domain specific terms, e.g. health-liefesci https://schema.org/docs/schemas.html	Cross-domain

Meta-portals facilitate evaluating data portals / repositories regarding applied metadata schemas. They enable discovery of and access to data portals, and often provide filters to choose portals based on metadata standards, e.g. re3data⁴¹. Some portals resp. long-term storage repositories, such as PANGAEA⁴², provide internal mappings of metadata to enable cross-domain usage of the provided information and thus, do not force researchers to implement a certain metadata schema. Furthermore, mapping tables, as provided by the W3C⁴³ or EOSC⁴⁴, support transforming existing metadata.

To facilitate the evaluation of existing metadata schemas, the following table provides an overview of the metadata scope (see checklist in section S4) for selected standards: x = structured elements are available; (x) = not all required elements are included; - = specific or structured elements are not available. Further details are available in Appendix, Table 4.

Table 3: Metadata scope for selected standards

	C1: Structuring of data	C2: Data formats and services	C3: Scientific results and publications	C4: Open data and licensing	C5: Quality information	C6: Provenance information	C7: Thematic linking and vocabularies	C8: metadata standards and standard interfaces
DataCite, OpenAIRE	x	(x)	x	x	-	(x)	x	Based on DataCite ⁴⁵ , OAI-PMH
Dublin Core	x	(x)	(x)	x	-	(x)	x	
GeoDCAT	x	x	x	x	x	(x)	x	Based on DCAT; uses ISO 19115 code lists and DataCite lists; provides extension points
ISO 19xxx	(x)	x	(x)	x	x	(x)	x	Standard widely used in public authority geoportals and catalogues

⁴¹ www.re3data.org

⁴² <https://www.pangaea.de>

⁴³ https://www.w3.org/2015/spatial/wiki/ISO_19115_-_DCAT_-_Schema.org_mapping, <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/NOTE-prov-dc-20130430/>

⁴⁴ <https://eosc-edmi.github.io/crosswalk>

⁴⁵ Differences: https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/data/use_of_datacite.html

S5: Mark and integrate extension points

During this phase, a synopsis of missing and unnecessary elements in the chosen schema should be prepared – include adding new elements, changing obligations for elements. Here, we use the GeoKur project as an example for developing a metadata profile.

The GeoKur Profile

In the GeoKur project, we chose GeoDCAT for the development of a specific metadata profile. GeoDCAT facilitates cross-domain sharing of descriptions and accessing of provided datasets. Due to the underlying linked data concept, GeoDCAT is shipped with several extension points, e.g. to link/integrate vocabularies, and enables the adaption of the schema to the project needs.

Namespaces

Prefix	Namespace URI	Specification
adms	http://www.w3.org/ns/adms#	[VOCAB-ADMS]
dc	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/	[DC11]
dcat	http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#	[VOCAB-DCAT-2]
dcatap	http://data.europa.eu/r5r/	[DCAT-AP]
dct	http://purl.org/dc/terms/	[DCTERMS]
dctype	http://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/	[DCTERMS]
dqv	http://www.w3.org/ns/dqv#	[DQV]
foaf	http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/	[FOAF]
geodcatap	http://data.europa.eu/930/	[GeoDCAT-AP]
gsp	http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#	[GeoSPARQL]
oa	http://www.w3.org/ns/oa#	[OA]
org	http://www.w3.org/ns/org#	[VOCAB-ORG]
prov	http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#	[PROV-O]
rdf	http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#	[RDF11-CONCEPTS]
rdfs	http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#	[RDF-SCHEMA]
skos	http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#	[SKOS-REFERENCE]
time	http://www.w3.org/2006/time#	[OWL-TIME]
vcard	http://www.w3.org/2006/vcard/ns#	[VCARD-RDF]
xsd	http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#	[XMLSCHEMA11-2]

Overview

The following overview is given for GeoDCAT's mandatory class Dataset (dcat:Dataset) - a conceptual entity that represents the published information: <https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/drafts/latest/#properties-for-dataset>

	Property	URI	Obligation	Cardinality	Range	Comment
1	title	dct:title	M	1	rdfs:Literal	Changed cardinality to 1
2	description	dct:description	M	1	rdfs:Literal	Changed cardinality to 1
3	contact point	dcat:contactPoint	M	1..n	vcard:Kind	Changed to mandatory
4	dataset distribution	dcat:distribution	R	0..n	dcat:Distribution	
5	keyword	dcat:keyword	R	0..n	rdfs:Literal	
6	spatial / geographic coverage	dct:spatial	M	1..n	dct:Location	Changed to mandatory
7	temporal coverage	dct:temporal	R	0..n	dct:PeriodOfTime	
8	theme / category	dcat:theme	M	1..n	skos:Concept	Changed to mandatory; Changed to enable linking to each ontology
9	creation date	dct:created	O	0..1	rdfs:Literal xsd:date xsd:dateTime	as or dateTime option removed
10	documentat ion	foaf:page	R	0..n	foaf:page	Changed to recommended; Links to publication
11	identifier	dct:identifier	M	1	rdfs:Literal	Changed to mandatory and changed cardinality to 1

						GeoKur internal unique identifier used to link resources, e.g. provenance, hierarchy, ...
12	is version of	dct:isVersionOf	O	0..n	dcat:Dataset	
13	landing page	dcat:landingPage	O	0..n	foaf:Document	Links to project website or dataset's website, e.g. CMIP website for all CMIP outputs
14	other identifier	adms:identifier	O	0..n	adms:Identifier	Links to DOI (for the dataset)
15	related resource	dct:relation	O	0..n	rdfs:Resource	Used to map hierarchy of datasets as "is part of" Relation
16	reference system	dct:conformsTo	M	1	dct:Standard	Changed cardinality to 1 Links to OGC EPSG Register ⁴⁶
17	spatial resolution as angular distance	geodcatap:spatialResolutionAsAngularDistance	O	0..n	dqv:Metric	
18	spatial resolution as distance	geodcatap:spatialResolutionAsDistance	O	0..n	dqv:Metric	
19	spatial resolution as equivalent scale	geodcatap:spatialResolutionAsScale	O	0..n	dqv:Metric	

⁴⁶ <http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/>

20	temporal resolution	dcat:temporalResolution	O	0..n	rdfs:Literal
21	was generated by	prov:wasGeneratedBy	O	0..n	prov:Activity
22	was used by	prov:wasUsedBy	O	0..n	prov:Activity
23	has quality annotation	dqv:hasQualityAnnotation	O	0..n	dqv:QualityAnnotation
24	has quality measurement	dqv:hasQualityMeasurement	O	0..n	dqv:QualityMeasurement

Obligations: M = Mandatory, R = Recommended, O = Optional

Details and Examples

In the following section, we describe our GeoKur profile in detail and provide several examples.

GeoKur Identifiers

In the GeoKur project, we developed three identifiers. The GeoKur-Data-Identifier provides a unique identifier for datasets published in the GeoKur metadata catalogue⁴⁷, being either input data for our analysis (e.g. with extended meta information), intermediate result or analysis results. We use the identifier to model dataset versioning, dataset structuring (hierarchies / series) and provenance. The GeoKur-Process-Identifier provides a link to the GeoKur geoprocessing workflow register. We use this register to describe building blocks for geoprocessing workflows, being (re-) used to describe dataset's provenance information, in particular the geoprocessing workflow. Furthermore, we developed a geospatial categories register, to enable semantic tagging of geoprocessing workflows with geospatial categories via GeoKur-Category-Identifier.

We use the following notation:

- <GeoKur-Data-Identifier> = `https://geokur-dmp.geo.tu-dresden.de/dataset/<producer>:<seriesname>:<product_name>`
- <GeoKur-Process-Identifier> = `https://geokur-dmp.geo.tu-dresden.de/processes#<process_name>`
- <GeoKur-Category-Identifier> = `https://geokur-dmp.geo.tu-dresden.de/pages/geospatial-categories-register#<categoryname>`

3 Contact Point

We decided to implement the contact point (`dcat:contactPoint`) using `vcard:kind`⁴⁸ and enabling the metadata provider to link a researcher or an organization.

Property	URI	Obligation	Cardinality	Range	Comment
name	<code>vcard:fn</code>	M	0..1	<code>rdfs:Literal</code>	Changed to mandatory
url	<code>vcard:hasURL</code>	O	0..1	<code>owl:Thing</code>	Links to orcid

```
dcat:contactPoint [ a vcard:Individual ;
  vcard:fn "First name Last name"@en ;
  vcard:hasURL <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3085-7457> ] ;
```

```
dcat:contactPoint [ a vcard:Organization ;
  vcard:fn "Organization name"@en ;
  vcard:hasURL <http://www.eea.europa.eu> ] ;
```

4 Distribution

To describe the distribution, we use the recommended class `dcat:Distribution` and only provide mandatory and modified properties in the following table. For a detailed description of all class properties, please use the following link: <https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/drafts/latest/#properties-for-distribution>.

Property	URI	Obligation	Cardinality	Range	Comment
access URL	<code>dcat:accessURL</code>	M	1..n	<code>rdfs:Resource</code>	
license	<code>dct:license</code>	R	0..1	<code>dct:LicenseDocument</code>	Modified to URL

⁴⁷ <https://geokur-dmp.geo.tu-dresden.de/>

⁴⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vcard-rdf/>

The following example is provided within the GeoDCAT description and modified regarding the license description:

```

dcat:distribution [ a dcat:Distribution ;
  dct:accessRights
<http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/metadata-
codelist/LimitationsOnPublicAccess/INSPIRE_Directive_Article13_1e> ;
  dct:description "NoiseContours_air_lnight"@en ;
  dct:format <http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/TIFF> ;
  dct:license <http://licenseurl.de> ;
  dcat:accessService [
dct:conformsTo <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/wms> ;
  dcat:endpointDescription
<https://noise.discomap.eea.europa.eu/arcgis/services/noiseStoryMap/NoiseContours_a
ir_lnight/ImageServer/WMServer?request=GetCapabilities&service=WMS> ;
  dcat:endpointURL
<https://noise.discomap.eea.europa.eu/arcgis/services/noiseStoryMap/NoiseContours_a
ir_lnight/ImageServer/WMServer> ] ;
  dcat:accessURL
<https://noise.discomap.eea.europa.eu/arcgis/services/noiseStoryMap/NoiseContours_a
ir_lnight/ImageServer/WMServer?request=GetCapabilities&service=WMS> ]

```

5 Keyword

A keyword is used to describe the dataset. As keywords are typically used for dataset discovery (and related implementations), we recommend to provide useful keywords.

```

dcat:keyword "Environmental Noise Directive"@en,
  "Noise map"@en,
  "agglomerations"@en,
  "noise source"@en ;

```

6 Spatial / Geographic Coverage

In the GeoKur project, the developed GeoDCAT profile is used to describe geospatial datasets published in a metadata catalogue / data management platform. Further, information about the spatial extent are included in a Geodashboard with proper visualization to describe provenance, quality and general metadata. Therefore, we changed the obligation of the spatial extent (dct:spatial, range of dct:Location) to mandatory.

Property	URI	Obligation	Cardinality	Range	Comment
bounding box	rdfs:Literal typed as gsp:wktLiteral	M	1	rdfs:Literal	Changed to mandatory

```

dct:spatial [
  rdf:type dct:Location ;
  dcat:bbox "POLYGON((-180 90,180 90,180 -90,-180 -90,-180 90))"^^gsp:wktLiteral ;
] ;

```

7 Temporal Coverage

The temporal coverage is described as start and end date, simplified for our GeoKur profile, using dates and not dateTimes.

Property	URI	Obligation	Cardinality	Range	Comment
start date	dcat:startDate	R	0..1	rdfs:Literal typed as xsd:date	

end date	dcat:endDate	R	0..1	rdfs:Literal typed as xsd:date
----------	--------------	---	------	--------------------------------------

```
dct:temporal [ a dct:PeriodOfTime ;
  dcat:endDate "2016-12-31"^^xsd:date ;
  dcat:startDate "2016-01-01"^^xsd:date ] ;
```

8 Theme / Category

A topic category as described in the GeoDCAT schema⁴⁹ is a high-level classification scheme to facilitate grouping and thematic description based on controlled vocabularies. Here, we modified the schema to enable linking to any useful / preferred vocabulary, not only linking to the INSPIRE / GEMET register. We enable two options:

```
dcat:theme <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/theme/hy> ,
  [ a skos:Concept ;
    skos:prefLabel "Floods"@en ;
    skos:inScheme [ a skos:ConceptScheme ;
      rdfs:label "GEOSS - Societal Benefit Areas, version 1.0"@en ;
      dct:issued "2010-08-25"^^xsd:date ] ] .
```

or (preferred)

```
dcat:theme <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/theme/ef>,
  <http://www.eionet.europa.eu/gemet/concept/12301>,
  <http://www.eionet.europa.eu/gemet/concept/3780>
```

9 Creation Date

The creation date describes, when the dataset was created or updated.

```
dct:created "2019-10-31"^^xsd:date ;
```

10 Documentation

The documentation refers to a document or a page about the dataset. We recommend to link the scientific publication, e.g. providing supplemental material with a detailed documentation, using a DOI as persistent and unique identifier.

```
foaf:page <https://doi.org/doi.../>
```

11 Identifier

In the GeoKur project, we developed an internal identifier to link a dataset, e.g. to link to previous versions, to structure datasets, e.g. in series / hierarchies or to link to dataset from provenance descriptions. The identifier is used in several tools, like in the metadata catalogue or in provenance visualization tools.

```
dct:identifier <GeoKur-Data-Identifier>
```

12 Version

Here, we model versioning using our GeoKur-Data-Identifier. To reduce redundancy, we only link to previous version and removed the property has version.

```
dct:isVersionOf <GeoKur-Data-Identifier>
```

⁴⁹ <https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/drafts/latest/#topic-category-originating-controlled-vocabulary-and-keyword-value---dataset-topic-category>

13 Landing Page

As described in the GeoDCAT schema, the landing page refers to a website that provides access to the dataset and/or additional information.

```
dcat:landingPage <http://www.myurl.de>
```

14 Other Identifier

We use this identifier to provide the dataset's DOI, preferably as link.

Property	URI	Obligation	Cardinality	Range	Comment
identifier	skos:notation	0	0..n	rdfs:Literal	Link to DOI resolver : <a href="https://dx.doi.org/<doi>">https://dx.doi.org/<doi>

```
adms:identifier <https://dx.doi.org/doi>
```

15 Related Resource

We reduce the complexity of provided relations to cover only is-part-of relation, used to model dataset hierarchies - dct:isPartOf is a sub property of dct:relation.

```
dct:isPartOf <GeoKur-Data-Identifier>
```

16 Reference System

We recommend using the OGC register: <http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/> to reference proper EPSG codes.

```
dct:conformsTo <http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/3035>
```

17 Spatial Resolution as Angular Distance

```
geodcatap:spatialResolutionAsAngularDistance "0.333"^^xsd:decimal
```

18 Spatial Resolution as Distance

```
dcat:spatialResolutionInMeters "5000"^^xsd:decimal
```

19 Spatial Resolution as Scale

```
geodcatap:spatialResolutionAsScale "0.5"^^xsd:decimal
```

20 Temporal Resolution

The following rules should be used to define duration value:
<https://www.w3.org/TR/xmlschema11-2/#duration> .

```
dcat:temporalResolution "P1D"^^xsd:duration
```

GeoKur specific Provenance Elements

Provenance information is of particular interest for the GeoKur project⁵⁰. We use provenance information to provide a concept⁵¹ for fully automatable graph transformation algorithm to generate provenance graphs for a geospatial workflow on several levels of detail and to provide user interfaces⁵² for the evaluation of fitness for use of a data. Here, we model a *workflow* as container for a set of linked *datasets* and *processes* describing a closed provenance graph. Relationships are modelled using the PROV-DM Relations Usage (prov:used), Generation (prov:wasGeneratedBy), and Derivation (prov:wasDerivedFrom).

Process and workflow profiles are described in the next paragraphs.

Following the GeoDCAT recommendations, we use the PROV to model provenance information.

Dataset

Any dataset with provenance information is modelled as prov:Entity.

Process

We describe a process - a building block of a workflow - as a sub type of prov:Activity. A process can have multiple input datasets. These datasets are used by the process (prov:used) to generate output datasets. The output datasets are generated by the process (prov:wasGeneratedBy) and derived from the input datasets (prov:wasDerivedFrom).

To overcome the complexity of provenance information for complex workflows and facilitate automated provenance script from geodata analysis scripts, like in the GeoKur project, we developed a separate (minimal) metadata profile for processes.

Property	URI	Obligation	Cardinality	Range	Comment
title	dct:title	M	1	rdfs:Literal	
description	dct:description	O	1	rdfs:Literal	describes the core characteristics
documentat ion	foaf:page	O	1	rdfs:Resource	links to documentatio n
used	prov:used	O	1...n	prov:Entity; geokur:Dataset	input datasets
generated	prov:generated	O	1...n	prov:Entity; geokur:Dataset	output datasets
category	geokur:has GeospatialCategory	O	1...n	geokur: GeospatialCatego ry	categorizes the process

As previously stated, we developed the <GeoKur-Category-Identifier> to annotate the workflow. Therefore, we provide the following initial list of categories in our GeoKur register⁵³, which will be extended during the project:

⁵⁰ Further information are published in: Figgemeyer, Henzen, Rümmler (2021): A Geo-Dashboard Concept for the Interactively Linked Visualization of Provenance and Data Quality for Geospatial Datasets. AGILE Conference. Henzen, Mäs, Bernard (2013): Provenance Information in Geodata Infrastructures. Vandenbroucke, D., Bucher B. and Crompvoets, J.: Geographic Information Science at the Heart of Europe.

⁵¹ Rümmler (2020): How to evaluate and reduce the complexity of geospatial provenance graphs? The Geospatial Sensing Conference.

⁵² <https://geokur-dmp2.geo.tu-dresden.de/provViewer>

⁵³ <https://geokur-dmp2.geo.tu-dresden.de/pages/geospatial-categories-register>

- geokur:Selection
- geokur:Transformation
- geokur:Reclassification
- geokur:Geometric
- geokur:Visualization
- geokur:Neighborhood
- geokur:Overlay
- geokur:Network
- geokur:Statistics
- geokur:Module

The following example shows, how to implement the extension. Note that we use `prov:wasGeneratedBy` by the inverted PROV-O default relation of `prov:generated` ().

```

ex:myActivity a geokur:Process,
    prov:Activity,
    dct:identifier <geokur-identifier>;
    dct:title "My Activity"@en;
    dct:description "Example Activity to showcase scheme"@en;
    prov:used ex:inputDsOne,
        <...> ,
        ex:inputDsX;
    geokur:hasGeospatialCategory <geoCategoryId>;
    foaf:page <https://linktopap.er> .

ex:outDsOne prov:wasGeneratedBy ex:myActivity .
ex:outDsOne prov:wasDerivedFrom ex:inputDsOne,
    <...>,
    ex:inputDsX.

ex:outDsTwo prov:wasGeneratedBy ex:myActivity ;
    prov:wasDerivedFrom ex:inputDsOne,
        <...>,
        ex:inputDsX.

ex:outDsX prov:wasGeneratedBy ex:myActivity ;
    prov:wasDerivedFrom ex:inputDsOne,
        <...>,
        ex:inputDsX.

```

In case the process that is involved to generate certain output datasets from certain input datasets is unknown, the PROV-O property `wasDerivedFrom` can be used. It states that a certain datasets was derived from another dataset, without referring to the process that was involved in this derivation. We implemented this property as the metadata field "was derived from" of GeoKur datasets.

Property	URI	Obligation	Cardinality	Range	Comment
was derived from	prov:wasDerivedFrom	O	1..nn	Prov:Entity; geokur:Dataset	Dataset(s) from which the current dataset was derived from.

Parameter

In our project, we need to distinguish datasets and parameters as inputs for process. We use a parameter to control a process, e.g. a buffer needs a buffer distance, and model the parameter as a sub type of `prov:Entity`.

Property	URI	Obligation	Cardinality	Range	Comment
id	prov:id	M	1	rdfs:Literal	

title	prov:label	M	1..n	rdfs:Literal	
type	prov:type	M	1	rdfs:Literal	type=parameter or Used to set parameter values, e.g. HABITAT=1
value	prov:value	O	0..1	rdfs:Literal	Used to define values, e.g. HABITAT=1

```
myParam a geokur:Parameter ;
  prov:id <GeoKur-Parameter-Identifier> ;
  prov:label "The parameter name"@en ;
  prov:type "input" ; # here we can define mandatory/optional or input/output
  prov:value "1"
```

or

```
myParam a prov:Entity ;
  prov:id <GeoKur-Parameter-Identifier> ;
  prov:label "The parameter name"@en ;
  prov:type "Parameter" ;
  prov:value "1" .
```

Workflow

A workflow links datasets and processes describing a closed provenance graph that are related by provenance statements (prov:used, prov:wasGeneratedBy, prov:wasDerivedFrom) as a workflow. Therefore, a workflow serves as container for closed provenance graphs. It can be attached with higher order meta information. As for processes, we implemented a minimal metadata profile for Workflows.

Property	URI	Obligation	Cardinality	Range	Comment
Title	dct:title	M	1	rdfs:Literal	
Description	dct:description	O	1	rdfs:Literal	Describes the core characteristics
Documentation	foaf:page	O	1	rdfs:Resource	Link to documentation
Source code	foaf:page	O	1...n	rdfs:Resource	Link to source code
Related datasets	geokur:hasRelatedDataset	O	1...n	prov:Entity; geokur:Dataset	Datasets that were involved in the workflow
Related processes	geokur:hasRelatedProcess	O	1...n	prov:Activity; geokur:Process	Processes that were involved in the workflow
Result	geokur:hasResult	O	1...n	prov:Entity; Geokur:Dataset	Datasets that resulted from the workflow

The following example shows, how to implement the extension:

```
ex:myWorkflow a geokur:Workflow;
  dct:identifier <geokur-identifier>;
  dct:title "My Workflow"@en;
  dct:description "Example Workflow to showcase scheme."@en;
  foaf:page <https://linktodocumentation.org>,
    <https://linktogithubsourcecode.org>,
    <https://linktoothergithubsourcecode.org>,
    <https://linktozenodo.org>,
    <https://linkto...> .
  geokur:hasRelatedDataset ex:inputDsOne,
```

```

    ex:inputDsX,
    ex:outDsOne,
    ex:outDsTwo,
    ex:outDsX,
    <...> .

geokur:hasRelatedProcess ex:myActivity,
    <...> .

geokur:hasResult ex:outDsTwo .

```

GeoKur specific Data Quality Elements

Quality information is a fundamental characteristic of data, providing the necessary information to determine the fitness for use. However, the quality of heterogeneous data, as used in the GeoKur, is described using different measures or metrics, on different levels of details and in different sources, e.g. metadata or publications.

To implement data quality, we use the data quality vocabulary (DQV), which offers common patterns to describe data quality, as recommended in the GeoDCAT schema. The following rules describe how to define data quality: <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/#quality-information>. We focus on the following two elements:

- dqv:QualityAnnotation represents feedback and quality certificates
- dqv:QualityMeasurement describes a metric value providing quantitative or qualitative information about the dataset

We developed an extension of the existing DQV classes with the following modifications:

- (1) providing meta quality descriptions for each quality metrics to better meet the required level of detail for the meta quality,
- (2) referencing information sources for data quality, in particular, to reference unstructured information, e.g. provided as long texts (supplemental material),
- (3) separating metric (and certificate / label) descriptions from the dataset metadata and measured values to enable reusing of descriptions, to facilitate semantic linking for the descriptions, e.g. across domains, and to provide mechanism for managing quality measures
- (4) referencing ground truth data to improve transparency and reproducibility.

As proposed in the DQV schema, we used the following ISO 19157⁵⁴ categories and (sub) classes as initial set for our ontology / register, which can be extended / linked by the metadata providers:

- iso:Completeness
- iso:LogicalConsistency
- iso:PositionalAccuracy
- iso:UsabilityElement
- iso:ThematicAccuracy
- iso:TemporalQuality

Meta quality as proposed by ISO 19157 is omitted, because we use certain aspects of meta quality to directly annotate the measurements.

⁵⁴ International Organization for Standardization: Geographic Information - Data Quality (ISO 19157:2013). First edition, Geneva, 2013.

We implemented a simplified quality ontology as machine-actionable endpoint⁵⁵ and automatically generated a related quality register as human-readable endpoint⁵⁶ using the initial set of categories and classes.

23 Quality Annotation

Quality annotations facilitate describing quality labels as summary of several quality metrics. The property has quality annotation implements the following description:

Property	URI	Obligation	Cardinality	Range	Comment
has quality annotation	dqv:hasQualityAnnotation	O	0..n	dqv:QualityAnnotation	

The property quality annotation implements the following description:

Property	URI	Obligation	Cardinality	Range	Comment
motivation	oa:motivatedBy	M	1	oa:Motivation	

```
<https://certificates.theodi.org/en/datasets/393> a dcat:Dataset ;
    dqv:hasQualityAnnotation :classificationQA .

:classificationQA
    a dqv:UserQualityFeedback ;
    oa:hasTarget <https://certificates.theodi.org/en/datasets/393> ;
    oa:hasBody :four_stars ;
    oa:motivatedBy dqv:qualityAssessment, oa:classifying ;
    dqv:inDimension :availability .
```

The annotation description, like the following example for the 4-stars quality label, should be separated in a register as described above:

```
:four_stars
    a skos:Concept;
    skos:inScheme :OpenData5Star ;
    skos:prefLabel "Four stars"@en ;
    skos:definition "Dataset available on the Web with structured machine-readable non proprietary format. It uses URIs to denote things."@en .
```

24 Quality Measurement

To facilitate the evaluation of fitness for use and enable the usage for certain (visualization) tools, we added several properties to the DQV quality measurement class, e.g. reference to ground truth or to quality information source.

Property	URI	Obligation	Cardinality	Range	Comment
is measurement of	dqv:isMeasurementOf	O	0..1	dqv:Metric	Links to a term in a register of qualified descriptions for geospatial quality indicators
value	dqv:value	O	0..1	rdfs:Literal	The result;

⁵⁵ https://geokur-dmp2.geo.tu-dresden.de/fuseki/dataset.html?tab=info&ds=/data_quality_elements

⁵⁶ <https://geokur-dmp2.geo.tu-dresden.de/pages/quality-elements>

					Can either be quantitative or qualitative; point or range
confidence	dqv:hasQualityMeasurement	O	0..n	dqv:QualityMeasurement	Used to describe the statistical quality of the value
spatial representativity	dct:spatial	O	0..1	dct:Location	Describes the validity of the quality measurement as spatial location
temporal representativity	dct:temporal	O	0..1	dct:PeriodOfTime	Describes the validity of the quality measurement as temporal extent
thematic representativity	geokur:thematic	O	0..1	rdfs:Resource	Describes the validity of the quality measurement for a thematic category by linking to a term that is defined in an ontology or vocabulary, e.g. in AGROVOC ⁵⁷)
source of information	geokur:source	O	0..1	geokur:Source	Describes the source of the quality information
ground truth	geokur:groundTruth	O	0..n	(dcat:Dataset)	Links to a ground truth dataset

We use the following properties to describe the source of information (geokur:Source):

Property	URI	Obligation	Cardinality	Range	Comment
label of source of information	rdfs:label	O	0..1	rdfs:Literal	Name of the source document
type of source of information	geokur:sourceType	O	0..1	rdfs:Resource	Links to a term in a register of qualified types of sources of information (scientific paper, ISO quality report, ...)
website of source of information	foaf:page	O	0..n	rdfs:Resource	Links to the website where the source of information can be found

```
<Geokur-Dataset-Identifier> dqv:hasQualityMeasurement [
  a dqv:QualityMeasurement ;
  dqv:isMeasurementOf geokur:thematicClassificationCorrectnessAsKappaCoefficient;
  dqv:value "...";
  dqv:hasQualityMeasurement [
    a dqv:QualityMeasurement ;
    dqv:isMeasurementOf <...>;
    dqv:value "...";
  ];
  dct:spatial <...> ;
  dct:temporal <...> ;
  geokur:thematic <...> ;
  geokur:groundTruthDataset <...> ;
  geokur:source [
    rdf:label "...";
    geokur:sourceType <...> ;
    foaf:page <...> ;
  ]
] .
```

⁵⁷ <https://agrovoc.fao.org/browse/agrovoc/en/>

The used quality indicators should be stored and made accessible in a quality register. In the GeoKur case, the quality register⁵⁸ is implemented as part of the data management system. Example: Implementation of the ISO quality indicator "thematic classification correctness" measured as "kappa coefficient".

```
geokur:thematicClassificationCorrectnessAsKappaCoefficient
  a dqv:Metric ;
  skos:definition "Coefficient to quantify the proportion of agreement of
    assignments to classes by removing misclassifications"@en ;
  skos:prefLabel "Thematic Classification Correctness as Kappa Coefficient"@en ;
  dqv:expectedDataType xsd:decimal ;
  dqv:inDimension geokur:thematicClassificationCorrectness .

geokur:thematicClassificationCorrectness
  a dqv:Dimension ;
  skos:definition "Comparison of the classes assigned to features or their
    attributes to a universe of discourse"@en ;
  skos:exactMatch iso:thematicClassificationCorrectness ;
  skos:prefLabel "Thematic Classification Correctness"@en ;
  dqv:inCategory geokur:thematicAccuracy .

geokur:thematicAccuracy a dqv:Category ;
  skos:definition "Accuracy of quantitative attributes and the correctness of
    non-quantitative attributes and of the classifications of features and their
    relationships"@en ;
  skos:exactMatch iso:thematicAccuracy ;
  skos:prefLabel "Thematic Accuracy"@en ;
  geokur:inRegister geokur:qualityRegister .
```

⁵⁸ <https://geokur-dmp.geo.tu-dresden.de/quality-register>

Appendix

Summary of GeoDCAT-AP Modifications

All changes are related to the class Dataset (dcat:Dataset)

	Property	Comment
1	title	Changed cardinality to 1
2	description	Changed cardinality to 1
3	contact point	Changed to mandatory
4	dataset distribution	
5	keyword	
6	spatial / geographic coverage	Changed to mandatory
7	temporal coverage	
8	theme / category	Changed to mandatory; Changed to enable linking to any ontology
9	creation date	dateTime option removed
10	documentation	Changed to recommended; Links to publication
11	identifier	Changed to mandatory and changed cardinality to 1 GeoKur internal unique identifier used to link resources, e.g. provenance, hierarchy, ...
12	is version of	
13	landing page	Links to project website or dataset's website, e.g. CMIP page for all CMIP outputs
14	other identifier	Links to DOI (for dataset)
15	related resource	Used to map hierarchy of datasets as "is part of" Relation
16	reference system	Changed cardinality to 1 Links to OGC EPSG Register ⁵⁹
21	was generated by	Included via PROV-O
22	was used by	Included via PROV-O
23	has quality annotation	Included via DQV
24	has quality measurement	Included via DQV

⁵⁹ <http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/>

Removed Elements

- publisher (R) (foaf:agent)
- creator (O) (foaf:agent)
- access rights (O) – just code list
- conforms to (O)
- frequency (O)
- is referenced by (O)
- language (O)
- qualified attribution (O)
- qualified relation (O)
- rights holder (O)
- sample (O)
- source (O) – use provenance instead
- topic category (O)
- type (O)
- update / modification date (O)
- version (O) – create new dataset and relation instead
- version notes (O)

Selected Metadata Standards and Scope

Table 4: Detailed overview of metadata scope for selected standards

	C1: Structuring of data	C2: Data formats and services	C3: Scientific results and publications	C4: Open data and licensing	C5: Quality information	C6: Provenance information	C7: Thematic linking and vocabularies
ISO 19xxx	Parents and data series can be found; <i>part of</i> relations are not available	Data format ⁶⁰ can be specified with name, link, and version Information about geodata services can be structured	There is no explicit DOI field for publications Documentation can be used to link to publication	License can be defined as use or access constraints with a structured code list; e.g. unrestricted	Quality information can be described via ISO 19157 as predefined structured elements	Provenance can be described as structured process step and sources with further optional process steps	Concepts can be named and cited via links to vocabularies
GeoDCAT	Relations can be defined, e.g. <i>part of, has part; new version of;</i> further extensions using DCAT relations	Data format can be linked via url Information about geodata services are structured as set of url and type (INSPIRE registry)	Publication can be linked as documentation DOI and other identifier can be set	License url can be linked. Further Access right can set as link / code list via INSPIRE	Quality can be described in structured and extendible elements via data quality vocabulary	Provenance information can be described as structured activities and entities via PROV-O	Concepts can be named and cited via links to vocabularies
Dublin Core	Relations can be defined, e.g. <i>is part of, has part; is</i>	Data format can be defined using IANA registry	No separate field for publication DOI and other identifier can be defined	License document and access rights can be defined	No separate fields for quality	Provenance information can be described as free text and sources	Concepts can be cited as link to vocabularies

⁶⁰ As CI_Citation element

	<i>new version of</i>	Services can only be defined as common Web services	as free text, e.g. URI			can be described in separate fields, but process information not	
DataCite, OpenAIRE	Relations can be defined, e.g. <i>is part of, has part, is new version of</i>	Defined as free text Information about geodata services can be linked, but not structured to be used in a GDI	Relations between data and publications can be defined DOI, ISBN and other related identifier can be set	License url can be set	No separate fields for quality	Relations <i>is derived from</i> and <i>is source of</i> can be used	Concepts can be named and cited via links to vocabularies